

Real time flood mapping using SAR imagery

Rakesh Kumar Sarmah, Dr. Santanu Sarma

Department of Geology, Cotton University, Guwahati, India

Correspondence details: Department of Geology, Cotton University, Guwahati, PIN-781001, Assam, India. Email: rakeshassam86@gmail.com (corresponding author), santanusarmagw1@gmail.com

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Abstract

Synthetic Aperture Radars (SAR) are the active remote sensing sensor and used for terrestrial remote sensing from the space platforms. In this paper the SAR imageries are used for the application of flood mapping and monitoring during the monsoon season when the optical remote sensing sensor fails to provide the cloud free clear imageries of parts of flood ridden Assam, India. Using pre-flood SAR imagery, permanent water bodies are delineated and cross validated using Sentinel 2B optical imagery with overall classification accuracy of 94.06%. SAR imagery during flood is processed to derive inundation map, cross validation is done using ISRO BHUVAN portal flood data. Radar backscatter variation in pre-flood and during flood period is studied for croplands and grasslands. Finally village level inundation map is prepared for the study area using village data available in District Census Handbook.

Key words: Flood; SAR; GIS; Inundation; Assam

Introduction

River flood is a common and frequent natural hazard occurring globally. Most common cause of river flooding is excessive or prolonged rainfall in upstream catchment with excess water flow through channels beyond the storage capacity resulting overflow of water crossing the bank and filling low lying lands (Rincon et al. 2018). Flooding threatens human lives, cause damage to property, industry, transportation system (Chang 2005). In a global scale, over 1.4 billion people get affected by flood in the last decade with about 1,00,000 loss of life (Ling et al. 2017). In Indian context, every year on an average 75 lakh hectares of land get submerged with loss of nearly 1,600 lives and damage of agriculture, houses and public utilities worth 1,805 crores

(NDMA 2008). Flood brings tenfold misery to people living in rural areas with outbreak of epidemics such as malaria and cholera with scarcity of drinking water (Disaster Management of India 2011). Due to the increased encroachment in flood plains, the frequency and intensity of flood get increases day by day affecting more population and causing greater economic loss (Alam and Muzzammil 2011).

Near Real Time information of flood is critical for emergency response and mitigation of flood risk. Satellite remote sensing with both active and passive sensors operating in visible, infrared, thermal and microwave spectral regions is extensively used for mapping flood event due to their high spatial and synoptic coverage (Kiran et al. 2019; Anusha and Bharathi 2020). But it is often difficult to get real time clear imagery as flood is often accompanied with cloudy weather. Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) is an active remote sensing technique capable of penetrating cloud, fog or smoke for acquiring images in all-weather condition both day and night (Shaikh et al. 2018).

Study area

The area in the study includes the Rani and Chayani Barduar administrative block of Kamrup – Metro and Rural districts of Assam, covering an area of 423.03 sq. km. This area is occupied by vast tract of unsettled agricultural / forest land and villages and is surrounded by the mighty river Brahmaputra in the north, the Kulshi river in the west, hills of Meghalaya plateau in the south and south-east and Guwahati city in the north-east (Figure 1). The area is a part of the Kulsi river system and all the streams are flowing towards north to meet the river Brahmaputra. Every year the area is flooded with water of the river Brahmaputra, Kulshi and its tributaries. Due to enhanced South-west monsoon rainfall activity over north eastern states, Assam and Meghalaya

witness heavy to very heavy rainfall in the month of July. The actual cumulative rainfall received by Assam and Meghalaya during June, July and August are 1239.4 mm and 2780.9 mm in comparison to normal rainfall of 1191.6 mm and 2349.4 mm respectively.

Fig.1: Study Area

Flood History

The annual flood inundation atlas for Assam and Bihar prepared by National Remote Sensing Centre (NRSC), Hyderabad using both optical and microwave remote sensing technique for viewing purpose (available on Bhuvan Portal, NRSC, ISRO) was referred for the history of flood occurrences in the study area. Integrating different flood events throughout the calendar year, flood inundation maps have been prepared since 1998 to 2010 (13 years) with a view to identify frequently flooded area, regulate land use in flood plain areas and to identify flood relief shelters (NRSC 2012). For inundation area calculation these maps are geo-referenced to bring them into

GIS environment. Out of 13 years of available maps, inundation history for the study area has been analyzed considering 10 years (2001-2010) of datasets. This analysis provides an overview on the severity of flood within the study area (Table 1).

Table -1: Area coverage of flood inundation

Year	Flooded area (km ²)	Percentage of flooded area (%)
2001	15.46	3.65
2002	36.32	8.59
2003	29.60	7.00
2004	32.51	7.69
2005	7.26	1.72
2006	22.12	5.23
2007	27.4	6.48
2008	29.22	6.91
2009	4.30	1.02
2010	10.08	2.38

Objective

In the present study the use of SAR imageries to identify the real time inundation extent of flood within the study area is considered. A particular day, 16th July, 2020 is selected based on the fact that heavy rainfall had occurred in Kamrup Rural and Metro districts of Assam and adjacent RiBhoi district of Meghalaya as reported by India Meteorological Department (IMD). Figure 2 shows cloud conditions seen in the INSAT-3D image over Central Assam and adjacent Meghalaya on 15th July, 2020 and state leading newspaper reporting flood on the above mentioned date.

Fig. 2: INSAT-3D image showing cloud condition and State leading newspaper reporting on flood

Materials and Methods

SAR Data

The Sentinel 1 mission is a constellation of two operational satellites Sentinel 1A and Sentinel 1B, launched by European Space Agency on April, 2014 and April, 2016 respectively. Both carry C Band Synthetic Aperture Radar (C-SAR) payload following sun-synchronous orbit with repeat cycle of 12 days (Potin et al. 2016; Raspini et al. 2018). These data are freely available in Copernicus Open Access Hub platform of European Space Agency (ESA). The Copernicus Open Access Hub is a platform offered by ESA to freely avail different Sentinel products. The available data are extensively used in critical decision making during the event of emergency such as natural disaster or humanitarian crisis (Filchev et al. 2020). These RADAR datasets can be analyzed using Sentinel Application Platform (SNAP), an open source architecture developed

by European Space Agency. A comparison is shown in Figure 3 between Sentinel 1 radar imagery and Sentinel 2 optical imagery for the study area on flooded dates. These pictures clearly portray the limitation of optical remote sensing during the hour of emergency.

Fig. 3: Optical vs. SAR imagery during flood

To achieve the exact inundation extent on a flooded date it is important to have data on permanent water bodies and their extent in pre flood season. Thus two imageries representing pre flood and during flood situations are downloaded. The pre flood imagery is a Sentinel 1A Ground Range Detected (GRD) product of 15th February, 2020 whereas the imagery during flood is a Sentinel 1B GRD product captured on 16th July, 2020. The details of the product have been summarized in the Table 2.

Table 2 Sentinel 1 product details

Satellite	Date and	Product	Acquisition	Spatial Resolution
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	Time	Type	Mode	
Sentinel 1A	15 Feb 2020, 14:31:22	Level-1 GRD	IW	10*10 m
Sentinel 1B	16 Jul 2020, 17:40:35	Level-1 GRD	IW	10*10 m

Fig. 4: Methodology Flowchart

Processing of the data

The downloaded data are processed using SNAP open source software. Pre-processing of the data is required to remove any distortion present and to enhance the quality of the image. Different steps are performed sequentially in pre-processing of the image. The raw data downloaded from Copernicus Open Access Hub comes in zip format and it can be directly processed in SNAP software step by step. As the product size of the raw data is high (1654 MB for pre flood and 3749 MB for during flood), to increase the processing speed a subset of the area of study is extracted defining geo coordinates of the desired extension. Application of the orbit file ensures orbital data accuracy; improve geocoding (Hong et al. 2017) and effects subsequent processing steps. Radiometric calibration technique converts pixel intensity or radar reflectivity (DN number) to radar cross section (RCS) or scattering cross section (Thomas WeiB 2018; Schmidt et al. 2020). The RCS is the measure of reflective strength of radar target and it is indicated by symbol 'sigma'. The value of 'sigma' depends upon shape, dielectric properties, orientation, roughness etc. of the target and these properties also vary for different observation angles, frequencies and polarizations. As the radar return signify proportion of energy scattered by distributed area correspond to the size of image pixel, a normalized measure is needed to relate the inferred target area derived from scattering cross section, to the actual geometrical area on the ground surface. This unit less normalized measure is defined as 'backscatter coefficient', 'differential radar cross section' or 'normalized radar cross section' denoted by 'sigma nought' (Woodhouse 2006; Sentinel user guide). Due to the low backscattering response, flooded area appears dark and strong backscattering from rough soil surface and vegetation cause land surfaces appear bright (Manjusree et al. 2012). 'Speckles' are random, high frequency noises

present in SAR images causing granular salt and peppery pattern with degradation of image quality as well as loss of information (White et al. 2015; Choi and Jeong 2019). Applying ‘speckle filtering’ technique, image quality can be enhanced. Different speckle filters are available in SNAP such as Gamma Map, Lee, Refined Lee, and Lee Sigma with different window sizes. Comparing different filters, Lee (5*5) window size is found suitable for the study. The side looking geometry of RADAR and topographic relief causes several geometric distortions such as foreshortening, layover, and shadow (Esmaeilzade et al. 2015; Chen et al. 2018). Geometric distortion caused by topography is corrected using Range Doppler terrain correction which uses a digital elevation model to rectify the location of each pixel. The process utilizes available orbital information in the metadata, radar timing annotations and slant to ground range conversion parameters with the reference DEM (Filipponi, 2019). For this study SRTM DEM with 3 arcsec and bilinear interpolation resampling technique has been used for geometrical correction. The final product is converted to decibel (dB) units using logarithmic transformation. Conversion of linear amplitude to decibels (dB) improve image display by compressing wide range of values and reducing impact of multiplicative noise (Flores-Anderson et al. 2019).

Results and discussion

In SAR polarimetry, horizontal polarization (H) indicates electric vector perpendicular to the plane of incidence and vertical polarization (V) indicates orthogonal to both horizontal polarization and direction of propagation (Zyl and Kim, 2011). Radar antenna can transmit a wave in one polarization and receive echoes in two orthogonal polarizations simultaneously (Elachi and Zyl, 2006). Sentinel 1 SAR provide dual polarization, VV and VH, with enormous

application potential such as climate zone classification (Hu et al. 2018), land cover classification (Banque et al. 2016), crop growth monitoring (Khabbazan et al. 2020).

Pre flood analysis

The pre-flood image analysis provides information about permanent water bodies so that there won't be any over estimation of flooded area during flood. Permanent water bodies contain smooth open surfaces acting as a specular reflector, scattering the radar energy away from the sensor. Thus relatively dark pixels appear in the image in comparison to non-water areas (Martinis and Rieke, 2015). The pre flood imagery of 15th February, 2020 is processed following the steps as mentioned above. The final terrain corrected product in dB for both VV and VH polarization are obtained. In comparison to VV, VH polarization generates well correctly defined surfaces and is found more suitable for demarcating flooded areas (Conde and Munoz, 2019). The most widely accepted technique in differentiating land pixels vs. water is the intensity thresholding method (López-Caloca et al. 2018). The backscattered value range can provide significant discrimination between water and non-water region. Careful observation of the histogram provides a threshold value to separate water bodies from other features (Conde and Munoz 2019; Zhang et al. 2020). By using a suitable band maths expression ($\text{Sigma0_VH_db} < -21.22$), the water pixels can be extracted. Validation of the result is carried out using cloud free Sentinel 2B optical imagery of dated 21st February, 2020. Total 12 reference points are collected to validate the permanent water bodies derived from SAR imagery with an overall classification accuracy of 94.06%. In figure 5 examples are showing for collection of reference points from permanent water bodies such as Deepor Beel lake and a pond.

Fig. 5: Examples showing Reference Points for validation of permanent water bodies

Topographic shadow shows dark tone not necessarily water pixels and are mainly found in forest areas at higher elevation. Similarly flat concrete surfaces occurring in and around airport premises such as airport runway, parking and some new construction sites also show low backscattering. Cross verification of topographic shadow in hilly region is done using Cartosat-1 DEM having spatial resolution of 1 arc second. High resolution LISS 4 imagery of dated 18th March, 2019 is used to cross check low backscattering features in and around Airport premises and other built-up areas (Fig. 6)

Table 3: Details of satellite data used for validation of permanent water bodies

Satellite	Sensor	Path	Row	Scene date	Resolution	Use
Resourcesat 2	LISS 4	110	53	18 March, 2019	5.8 m	Validation of Airport, Built-up, Water bodies and Preparation of LULC map
Agency ESA	Satellite Sentinel 2B	Orbit No 133	Tile No T46RCP	21 February, 2020	10 m (Band 2,3,4)	Validation of water bodies
Cartosat-1 DEM					1 arc sec	Validation of Topographic shadows

Fig. 6: Low backscattering values (dark tone) in Airport parking and hill region

Total area of permanent water bodies is found to be 14.03 km² after necessary cross verification. The permanent water bodies within the study area are mainly stretch of river Brahmaputra, river Kulshi, Deepor Beel Lake, Chandubi Lake and some ponds. Extraction of pre flood water bodies are shown with the example of the Chandubi Lake within the study area (Figure 7).

Fig. 7: Pre flood permanent water bodies (with an example of Chandubi Lake)

During flood analysis

Flood extent delineation is done using Sentinel 1B GRD product captured on 16th July, 2020. The image is pre-processed to final terrain corrected dB product of both VV and VH polarization.

The histogram has been analyzed and a threshold backscatter value (dB = -24.26) has been identified to separate water and non-water pixels from the image (Figure 8a).

Total area undergoing inundation is calculated in GIS environment and found 26.56 km². Excluding areas of permanent water bodies, the total inundation on 16th July, 2020 is found to be 12.53 km² (Figure 8b). The cross verification of the result is often difficult because field work during flood is challenging (Uddin et al. 2019). There is also unavailability of cloud free optical data for the month of July, 2020. For accuracy assessment the reference data should be of higher quality and in case of remote sensing its spatial resolution should be finer than the map data (FAO, 2016). Due to such limitation, secondary data available in ISRO BHUVAN portal regarding recent Assam Flood, 2020 is used as reference data. In this platform inundation layers of major flood dates are available. The inundation layer of 16th July, 2020 is accessed in pdf format and visualized in GIS environment after geo-referencing the same using prominent ground control points. *Visual inspection*, though not sufficient, is the first step of accuracy assessment to proceed further. A *difference image* is a graphic and easy to understand method in comparing any two registered map of the same area (Congalton, 1999). Superimposing SAR derived water bodies over the reference layer gives similarity in distribution of the flood. A *difference image* is created showing areas of agreement in black and areas of disagreement in white. It has been observed that black region is well distributed inside the white region i.e. the reference image is a combined representation of scattered inundation patches derived from SAR analysis (Figure 8c).

Fig. 8a: Histogram showing threshold to distinguish water pixels during flood, 8b: SAR derived flood inundation, 8c: A *difference image* for validation

Backscatter Coefficient (dB) variation in cropland and grassland

Backscatter behavior in rural flooding usually shows a decrease in dB values because open flood water acts as specular surface and radar energy is forward scattered with less hindrance in comparison to urban flooding (Lin et al. 2019). The backscattered signal strength depends on sensor specification such as wavelength, polarization and incidence angle along with surface

roughness, geometry and water content (O’Hara et al, 2019). Inundated areas can be differentiated by significant negative change in backscatter value in wet season image in comparison to dry season (Clement et al, 2018).

The inundation layer during flood is superimposed over Land Use Land Cover (LULC) map prepared from LISS-4 satellite imagery with spatial resolution 5.8 m. It is found that inundation is mainly witnessed in agricultural croplands and grasslands. Cropland is one of the dominant land use class covering 153.73 km² i.e. almost 36 % of total study area out of which 8.86 km² areas are found inundated. Grassland occupies 15.68 km² of the total area out of which 2.03 km² areas got inundated. To analyze backscattered coefficient (dB) variation in pre-flood and during flood condition, total ten grids of agricultural land and three grids of grassland with dimension 500m × 500m are selected from different locations randomly (Fig. 9a). The mean pixel value within each grid for both the land use classes are calculated (Table: 4) and compared for both the seasons (Fig. 9b and 9c). Mean dB value ranges between -13.31 to -20.00 in pre-flood for croplands and grasslands and it ranges between -24.10 to -26.19 during flood period.

Table 4 Backscatter Coefficient (dB) variation in pre and during flood in different grids of cropland and grassland

Grids showing agricultural lands undergoing inundation	Pre-flood Backscattering Coefficient (dB) Mean	During flood Backscattering Coefficient (dB) Mean	Grids showing grasslands undergoing inundation	Pre-flood Backscattering Coefficient (dB) Mean	During flood Backscattering Coefficient (dB) Mean
1	-17.74	-25.44	1	-18.01	-25.46
2	-13.31	-25.00	2	-16.20	-27.03
3	-14.87	-25.23	3	-15.49	-26.19
4	-16.72	-25.19			
5	-20.00	-25.94			
6	-18.01	-25.79			

7	-14.84	-24.97
8	-16.55	-24.91
9	-16.92	-24.10
10	-18.94	-24.94

Fig 9a: 500m × 500m grids showing agricultural land and grassland undergoing inundation,

9b: Graph showing mean dB change in two seasons for agricultural land and 9c: grassland

Village wise flood inundation statistics

The District Census Handbook (DCHB) published by Census of India (2011) provides 4523 information on demographic and socio-economic data at the lowest administrative unit i.e. village and town (ward) level. Circle wise available village map and other allied information are

extracted from DCHB of Kamrup and Kamrup (Metro). This village map is integrated with SAR derived flood inundation layer and area statistics of flood inundation for each village have been calculated in GIS environment. Based on flood concentration villages are classified in three categories: High inundation (> 10% of total area), Moderate inundation (10-5% of total area) and Low inundation (5-1 % of total area). Inundation less than 1% area are ignored due to the fact that minor pixels of inundation are common in many villages and are considered having less significance. It has been observed that under Rani Development block; 07 villages fall in high, 03 villages in moderate and 19 villages in low inundation category. In Chayani Barduar block 03 villages fall in high, 11 villages in moderate and 18 villages in low inundation category (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Village wise floodwater inundation

Conclusion

In this study, real time assessment of flood scenario is performed in a part of flood ridden state Assam using Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) imagery. The optical data during high flood months are covered with cloud to identify ground reality effecting disaster response decision. The study is conducted in GIS environment using SNAP and ArcGIS. The SAR derived permanent water bodies are verified with Sentinel 2B imagery of similar date with an overall classification accuracy of 94.06%. The dark pixels other than flood are cross verified using high resolution LISS-4 imagery, Google Earth and Cartosat1 DEM. Flood inundation map obtained from SAR is validated using ISRO BHUVAN portal derived inundation map for the particular day. A *difference image* between SAR inundation and reference map show strong agreement in terms of spatial distribution. The extraction of final flood inundation show total 10 villages within the area undergo high inundation, 14 villages moderate inundation and 37 villages low inundation. The variation of backscatter coefficient (dB) in pre-flood and during flood conditions are analyzed for dominant land uses undergoing inundation and clear distinction has been observed in both dry and wet conditions. Real time mapping of natural disaster like this help rapid decision making during the time of emergency.

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Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

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